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Individuals, Organizations, and the Economy: All Suffer When Workplace Hazards Are Ignored!

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ABSTRACT

Work accounts for one-third of one's adult life. If the state of the place of work is unfavorable – regardless of where, when, how large, or what kind – negative health consequences are certain to occur. When it comes to health and safety in the Middle East (ME), it is worth mentioning that the ME Safety Statistics have shown significant changes in safety rules over the last decade. However, considerable work still needs to be done; this will be true for regions all over the world until all workplaces are accident-free. In this paper, the occupational health and safety (OHS) in Lebanon — a small country in the Middle East, with an area of 10,452 km², a population of 4 million and nearly 2 million refugees from neighboring ME countries, and a service-oriented economy — is examined. The study aims to outline the magnitude of the problem and identify areas for potential research and interventions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, work-related accidents or diseases claim the lives of 6,300 individuals every day, or more than 2.3 million deaths every year, 340 million injured every year, and 160 million who suffer from work-related illnesses. The International Labor Organization's (ILO) projections for the years to come are only expected to climb with time, demonstrating both the poor health conditions that the world's working population is experiencing and the lack of concern for changing those conditions. The human cost of daily adversity is enormous, and the annual economic cost of poor occupational safety and health policies in some countries, like Lebanon, is estimated to be 4% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Given the prevalence of numerous threats that contribute to poor worker health, Lebanon is eerily similar to the ordeals of other countries, particularly developing ones.

Most businesses in Lebanon do not adhere to legally mandated minimum safety and health standards, and employees who are injured at work do not dare to assert their rights for fear of losing their jobs. As a result, they are responsible for their own treatment in case of a workplace accident. Due to a lack of official labor protection mechanisms, whether through inspections by the Ministry of Labor or issuing decrees and decisions that emphasize the importance of workers' compensation, the legal provisions relating to workers' compensation for accidents that affect them remain merely ink on paper.

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When performing dangerous tasks with their bare hands, such as chopping wood and steel or dealing with poisonous chemicals, some workers may not wear any type of personal protection equipment. Many workers also retain bad posture throughout their tasks, increasing their chances of getting chronic back or neck discomfort for the remainder of their lives. They may work in a filthy but apparently safe environment, but they are actually surrounded by unknown and potentially carcinogenic substances and biological dangers.

Workers are not to blame for what looks to be carelessness. More than 80% of Lebanon's population presently lives in poverty as a result of a mix of bad political and economic conditions. Workers accept workplace dangers because they are too busy putting food on the table for themselves and their families. Because of this vicious cycle of poverty and poor health – as well as a lack of means to get out – workers are either unable to fully understand the impact of the state of their work on their health, or cannot afford to purchase protective gear, risking being fired if they raise their concerns with management, or go without a salary while pursuing jobs under safer conditions.

2. SOURCES OF THE PROBLEM

The problem stems from the overall management of the workplace health and safety. Policymakers in countries, such as Lebanon, frequently underestimate the need for safe and healthy workplace and, consequently, fail to incorporate Health, Safety and Environment (HSE) in the country's priority list. The lack of implementation of present government legislation, as well as the resources required by the Ministry of Labor to prosecute violators, are all hurdles to employee protection in Lebanon.

By addressing the issue of occupational hygiene, many of Lebanon's problems will certainly be relieved. With technological advancements and increased productivity, such measures could improve worker health and life expectancy, decrease the number of people who quit work early due to illness or injury, lower the social and health-care costs, maximize the worker's potential, and lead to more effective and efficient labor processes.

By all means, employers must be held responsible for workplace health and safety issues. Management should be required to set aside a specific budget for acquiring the necessary equipment to monitor and mitigate occupational dangers, and hire occupational hygienists. Occupational hygiene experts identify potential dangers in the workplace before they arise, assess the risk on human health, and, if all else fails, apply appropriate control measures with respect to physical, chemical and biological hazards. By eliminating workplace hazards, occupational hygienists can then focus on prevention rather than on therapy, which is the best option.

3. INTERNATIONAL LEGISLATION

The topic of workplace safety and compensation regarding work-related injuries have gained center stage in international laws. The International Labor Organization (ILO), for instance, has provided recommendations, and was engaged in treaties and international conventions to regulate this issue. In 1921, for instance, the ILO issued the 12th Convention on Compensation for Work Accidents in Agriculture: “Each Member of the International Labor Organization which ratifies this Convention undertakes to extend to all agricultural wage-earners its laws and regulations which provide for the compensation of workers for personal injury by accident arising out of or in the course of their employment.”

On the other hand, Agreement No. 25 of 1927, relating to health insurance for agricultural workers, mandated health insurance for agricultural workers, both manual and non-manual workers who work for agricultural companies, including trainees, with the possibility of exempting some specific groups, in addition to the exemption of those who are covered by an alternative health-care system. According to Article 21, paragraph 1, of Convention No. 184 on safety and health in agriculture, "Agricultural employees are covered by an insurance system or social security against sustained injuries, fatal and non-fatal, disability, and other health work-related risks, which provides them with protection that is equivalent to at least that provided to workers in other industries."

The first Article of the International Labor Organization's Convention No. 17 on Compensation for Accidents Act of 1925 stated: "Everyone pledges to." If a member state of the International Labor Organization ratifies this Convention, it guarantees that workers wounded in a workplace accident or their dependents will be compensated in a condition that is at least comparable to the parameters stated in this agreement." This agreement, however, "Persons who carry out incidental, unrelated work" are exempt from its rules. Have a job or an employer's project, workers in their homes, and family members The sole proprietor who lives in his own home and works for himself Non-manual workers whose earnings surpass a maximum specified by national laws or regulations" were likewise excluded from Article 3 of the Convention under Article 2, paragraph 2. Mariners, fishers, and others who benefit from a system with at least equal benefits. The advantages set forth in this agreement, as well as Article 4, do not apply to workers employed by farmers who are bound by their own agreements. Article 5 of this agreement specifies the persons who are entitled for compensation as a result of work-related accidents, namely the injured worker or the persons whom he supports in the event of permanent disability or death. Article 7 states obliges an additional payment in case the concerned injured person requires help from someone else. As regards Article 11 of the Convention, it provided freedom to countries to determine the appropriate compensation to the worker in the event that insurance companies or the employers were unable to do so.

Occupational diseases are defined in Convention No. 18 of 1925 with regard to compensation for workers in the event of occupational diseases, and amended by Convention No. 34 of 1934, which in turn was replaced by Convention No. 121 in 1964; its name was changed to Injury Work Benefits Agreement. This agreement restored the exceptions contained in Agreement No. 17. Article 6 states that cases that involve compensation for a work-related accident is illness, incapacity to perform work, loss of earning capacity, partially or wholly, loss of livelihood for the assigned categories of beneficiaries as a result of breadwinner's death. This agreement necessitated countries to compile a list of occupational diseases and work accidents that they consider to be work-related accidents, according to Articles 7 and 8. Article 9 stipulates that compensation includes medical care and sick pay cash benefits where the worker is unable to make money. This continues so long as the case necessitates it. Also, Convention No. 42 on compensation for workers in the event of occupational diseases, as amended by the aforementioned Convention No. 121, came into force in 1934.

With regard to Convention No. 24 of 1927 concerning Sickness Insurance for Workers in industry, so Industry, trade and domestic workers, Article 1 obliged the ratifying countries to set up a system of compulsory health insurance" for manual and non-manual workers who work in industrial and commercial establishments, including home and domestic workers, as per Article 2 paragraph 1 On the other hand, paragraph 2 of Article 2 allowed some exceptions in the provisions of this contract, as regards temporary work, casual work, workers whose wages exceed an amount determined by the applicable law, workers who do not receive cash wages, domestic workers whose work type deviates from that of other paid ordinary workers, workers whose age is specified is determined by applicable laws, and the employer's family members. Article 2 paragraph 3 of compulsory insurance also excluded persons who benefit from health insurance that corresponds to the benefits stated in this agreement.

In this context, Convention No. 37 on Insurance against employee disabilities in industrial and commercial enterprises, liberal professions, domestic workers in their homes and domestic servants have been implemented in Agreement No. 128 in the year 1967, the name of which has become an agreement on invalidity, old-age and survivors' benefits.

4. THE LEBANESE LAW

Work-related accidents in Lebanon are governed by the Emergency, Protection and Prevention Labor Law, Accidents de Travail, promulgated by Legislative Decree No. 136 dated 9/16/83, which is the legislation-in-force until the entry into effect of the provisions of the National Social Security Fund Law that are related to work emergencies and occupational diseases.

According to Article 1 of the law, the employer is responsible for the sudden injuries that are caused by an external factor and which is inflicted on the employee due to the implementation of a work contract or as a result of implementing the contract. According to Article 17, the employer shall bear all medical, surgical and medicinal expenses, including:

- Hospital expenses, in addition to the cost of installing, maintaining and renewing limb prosthetic machines and other medical and surgical instruments that are necessary for the treatment and recovery of the injured worker, regardless of the duration of the worker's absence from work as a result of the work-related accident. Article 12 of the law obligates employers to ensure that employees have reasonable plans available for compensation and medical treatment.

In order to apply the law, Article 1 requires the following:

- the injured person is a wage-earner under an employment contract as per Article 624, paragraph 1 of the Lebanese Code of Obligations and Contracts.
- the accident is of work-emergency type that is caused by an external and sudden factor that led to bodily harm.

A mental disorder is regarded as a bodily injury. A disease is not considered work-related if it occurs in an excessively slow manner whilst the employee is carrying out the work, such as slow poisoning from water that is placed at the disposal of the employee. On the other hand, rapid poisoning caused by a contaminated drink is regarded as an emergency that deserves compensation.

- the emergency was the result of employment implementation or because of it.

A work emergency refers to the accident that the employee is exposed to during the course of his work, going to or returning from work, provided that going to or returning from are done without stopping or deviating from the normal course for a reason that is independent of work.

- the damage that is being complained of was the result of work emergency; that it, there is a direct causal link between the two, where the injury or the resulting damage is the result of the emergency that is being complained of.

Article 31 of the law states that an emergency compensation work claim shall be filed within a period of one year from the date of the accident, or from the outcome of the investigation, or following the cessation of temporary compensation payment. This period is regarded as a waiver period that is not cut or stopped, as is the case with the passage of time when the worker's right to claim compensation is no longer applicable.

As for the amount of compensation, the law distinguishes between injury that leads to total or partial disability. Compensation depends on the age of the beneficiary and the manner of death. Article 3 specifies the compensation accrued to a wage earner who sustains a total disability, and whose wage does not exceed the official minimum wage, as follows:

- 800 days of his average wage, if he is under 35 years of age;
- 700 days of his average wage, if he is over 35 years of age and under 50 years of age;
- 600 days of his average wage, if he is over 50 years of age.

In the event that the wage exceeds the official minimum wage, then the employee is entitled to receive, in addition to the above-mentioned compensations, a quarter of the compensation for the portion of wages that exceeds the minimum wage and up to double this limit, or one-eighth (1/8), of the compensation for the portion that exceeds about twice the official minimum wage.

In the event of partial disability, Article 4 of the decree states that an injured person has the right to receive compensation that is commensurate with the loss of the earning ability. This compensation shall reflect the case of whether the disability is permanent. If the damage is listed in the appendix attached to the work emergency law, then the injured employee shall receive a compensation that is equal to the percentage specified in the appendix. However, if the disability is not mentioned in the appendix, then the Labor Arbitration Council shall decide the compensation amount, taking into account the injured person's experience and work competence.

Article 5 states that an injured person has the right, from the very first day following the accident, for compensation of up to nine months, which is equal to $\frac{3}{4}$ th of the last daily wage; this wage is divided by six if the wage is weekly, by twelve if the wage is every 15 days, and by twenty-five if the wage is monthly. The daily compensation shall be made at the place and time where the wages normally take place; the time period between two consecutive payments shall not exceed fifteen days.

The employer shall also bear responsibility for all medical treatment expenses, regardless of the treatment period and cost. The employer is obligated to secure insurance contracts with insurance companies to guarantee compensation and treatment, according to Article 12 of the Work Emergency Law.

In the event of death, Article 6 of the Labor Emergency Law states the following: if the deceased employee's wages do not exceed the official minimum wage, his heirs shall receive a maximum compensation for 500-day wages; in case the wages do not exceed the minimum wage, then the heirs of the employee will be entitled to only one-fourth of the compensation related to the portion of wages that exceeds the official minimum wage and up to twice that limit, as well as $\frac{1}{8}$ th of the compensation that exceeds twice the official minimum wage. Article 10 prohibits the heirs of a foreign employee from compensation if they were found outside of Lebanon during the accident, with the exception of nationals of countries which grant Lebanese citizens the same rights as their own citizens.

In addition to the aforementioned compensation, the employer shall bear the burial expenses up to twice the official minimum wage. It should be noted in this context that compensation for death under this law does not belong to the legal heirs but to the rightful holders specified in the special law issued on 2/8/1974, which concerns the appointment of the rightful holders to receive compensation for dismissal from service.

5. HEALTH WORKERS' SAFETY NEGLECTED DURING COVID-19

Lebanese authorities have shown a callous disregard for the protection of healthcare workers at the front lines of the Covid-19 pandemic. The country has had an alarming surge of cases that is threatening to overwhelm the healthcare system.

Government institutions, including the Health Ministry, National Social Security Fund, and security agencies such as the military and Internal Security Forces, owe private and public hospitals large sums of money. Their failure to meet their financial obligations severely restricts hospitals' ability to maintain sufficient staffing levels and protect staff from infection. The authorities have also failed to stop violent attacks against healthcare workers. The pandemic has had a significant mental and emotional toll on the workers.

Lebanon's economic crisis predates the pandemic. The national currency has lost more than 80 percent of its value in the past year. Poverty rates have doubled, unemployment has skyrocketed, and inflation exceeded 500 percent.

The economic crisis has had a devastating impact on the healthcare sector. Medicines and medical supplies, most of which are imported, are in short supply. The value of nurses' and doctors' salaries has declined rapidly, triggering a mass exodus. The pandemic then placed an additional strain on a healthcare sector already in crisis. Hospitals' capacities have been stretched, their costs have risen, and yet the government is not disbursing the funds it owes them.

Under the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, which Lebanon has ratified, Lebanon is obligated to minimize the risk of occupational accidents and diseases, including by ensuring workers have health information and adequate protective clothing and equipment. This means providing healthcare workers and others involved in the COVID-19 response with appropriate training in infection control and with appropriate protective gear. In the context of the right to life where a lack of adequate PPE creates a foreseeable life-threatening situation, failure to provide adequate PPE to health workers exposed to Covid-19 may violate states' obligations to protect life.

Lebanon has had an exponential increase in Covid-19 cases and related deaths since October. Multiple full or partial lockdowns have been poorly enforced and have not stemmed the rise of Covid-10 cases, in large part due to the lack of an emergency social safety net that would enable working people to stay at home. Critics have accused the government of not having a cohesive, long-term strategy to deal with the pandemic.

The Lebanese authorities have also failed to address the economic crisis that has endangered people's basic rights. The World Bank said that the "deliberate lack of effective policy action by authorities has subjected the economy to an arduous and prolonged depression." The World Bank said that this lack of action is likely to cause Lebanon's economic crisis to be "deeper and longer than most economic crises."

5.1 Overworked and Underpaid

The Covid-19 pandemic has placed additional strains on a healthcare system already in crisis due to the government's failure to address the economic crisis and pay hospitals their dues. Various public sector entities, including the Health Ministry, National Social Security Fund, Internal Security Forces, and the army cover some medical costs for their personnel or residents covered under certain health insurance schemes, but the government has not disbursed a large share of those payments to hospitals.

The hospitals' precarious economic situation forced many to lay off significant numbers of staff in 2019, making them ill-prepared to face the Covid-19 pandemic. On top of that, the delay in paying doctors and nurses, the 80 percent decline in the value of healthcare workers' real income, and the lack of faith in the government's ability to address the multiple crises Lebanon is facing, have prompted an exodus from Lebanon of doctors and nurses – many of whom were among the most qualified.

Private and public hospitals have adopted cost-saving measures that have negatively affected their staff. Some have slashed salaries or forced staff to work half time. Others have started treating overtime hours as regular hours, instead of paying time and a half for overtime, as Lebanese labor law stipulates. Still, others have switched from paying their staff in US dollars to Lebanese pounds either at the official exchange rate or at a slightly higher rate that is considerably less than half the unofficial market rate.

5.2 Lack of Personal Protective Equipment

The failure of the government to pay hospitals their dues has made it difficult for the latter to purchase adequate supplies of personal protective equipment, prices for which have increased drastically due to the national currency's depreciation.

In this respect, the World Health Organization (WHO) has issued interim guidance on Covid-19 concerning the rights, roles, and responsibilities of healthcare workers. Employers and managers should provide workers with infection prevention and control masks, gloves, goggles, gowns, hand sanitizer, soap and water, and cleaning supplies in sufficient quantity such that workers will not have to incur their own expenses. Workers have the right to remove themselves from a situation that they have reasonable justification to believe presents an imminent and serious danger to their life or health, and to be protected from any resulting retaliation.

Further, the World Health Organization has indicated that medical masks should be worn by all healthcare workers interacting with Covid-19 patients and that respirator masks should be worn by those conducting aerosol-generating procedures. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention stated that regular face masks do “not provide the wearer with a reliable level of protection from inhaling smaller airborne particles and [are] not considered respiratory protection,” and recommends that health workers wear respirators where possible.

5.3 Attacks on Healthcare Workers

During the pandemic, some healthcare workers have become targets of violent attacks by patients and their families, especially as hospitals were no longer able to admit new patients. Some estimates indicate that there is at least one serious attack on a doctor every month, amid “judicial laxity” in holding the attackers – often people with “political backing” – accountable.

5.4 Mental Health Toll

The pandemic, its unrelenting spread across the country, and the failure by the government to adequately respond to the pandemic and support healthcare workers, has taken a mental and emotional toll.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In Lebanon, most companies do not meet the minimum statutory health and safety requirements, and workers who are exposed to work accidents do not dare assert their rights for fear of losing their jobs; therefore, they bear the cost of their own treatment as a result of a work-related accident, which normally should be borne by the employer.

Given the lack of formal Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) mechanisms, either through multi-level inspections by the Department of Labor or through the adoption of ordinances and decisions that emphasize the importance of worker protection, compensation simply remains ink on paper. It is necessary that the social rights of people are at the forefront of government priorities and do not change with changing governments and ministers. By all means, being aware of a workplace safety will reduce health difficulties for employees and save the Lebanese government millions of dollars in healthcare costs. The constant maintenance of health and illness prevention affects not only the workers but also the company as a whole, as well as the whole country.

We must ensure that factory managers, supervisors, and employees have basic awareness of OSH, both in terms of practicalities and rights, at the workplace level. Although the focus will always be on prevention, all employees must be aware of what to do in the event of an accident or emergency. In recent years, numerous stakeholders have conducted a significant amount of safety training. The decrease in the number of workplace fires and accompanying fatalities, for instance, demonstrates the success of these measures and the potential lives and livelihoods saved.

Workers must be assisted in better understanding their workplace safety rights, such as the right to use personal protective equipment when appropriate, the right to quit hazardous employment, and the right to seek assistance from the labor inspectorate, among other things. Employers, too, have an important role to play and must be well aware of their responsibilities. They should make workplace safety a high priority. Money spent on safety is an investment that will benefit not only the workers but also the company.

Establishing safety committees at companies with more than 50 employees must be a top priority. Safety committees can play a vital role in bringing worker and employer representatives together. They will serve as a conduit for worker participation in enhancing workplace safety, necessitating the provision of free and equitable opportunities for workers to select their own safety committee representatives. Furthermore, the question of worker safety and worker rights are inextricably linked. Workers who are empowered and aware play a critical role in ensuring workplace safety. In this regard, trade unions play a critical role, and they must be permitted to form and operate freely across all industries. Workers and their organizations must be empowered so that they can become active participants.

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In the following annex, background information on employment law in Lebanon is provided.

Annex: Employment Law in Lebanon

The Ministry of Labor: Responsibilities

Labour inspections are the responsibility of the Department of Labour Inspection, Prevention and Safety (DLIPS) under the Labour Relations Authority of the Ministry of Labour.

The National Social Security Fund (NSSF) carries out inspection services to verify social security contributions.

Law that covers organisation and functional composition:

- Lebanese Labour Law of 1946 and its amendments, in particular 1962
- Decree No. 3273 of 26 June 2000 on labour inspection
- Decree No. 112 of 12 June 1959 regarding status of public officials
- Order No. 161/1 of 18 February 1999 concerning the re-evaluation of transport indemnities
- Decree No. 128/ 2 of 17 February 2001 relating to the elaboration of inspection programmes.

Lebanese Labour Law is applicable to all employees and employers except for domestic and agricultural workers, enterprises limited to family members and public servants.

The Department of Labour Inspection, Prevention and Safety supervises the implementation of all laws, regulations, decrees and rules pertaining to the terms and conditions of employment, and the protection of workers in the workplace, including the provisions of international Labour Conventions approvals. Labour inspectors ensure the supervision of compliance with regulations in relation to conditions of employment and protection of workers including occupational health and safety. In addition, they monitor whether the trade unions and occupational associations comply with relevant laws, monitor compliance with protection and safety measures in family enterprises and the work of private employment agencies.

Under their functions they also investigate collective labour disputes. They are also involved in conciliation and the control of work permits for foreign workers.

Among the labour inspectors, some of them are generic who oversee inspecting conditions and others are occupational health and safety inspectors.

The Department of Labour Inspection, Prevention and Safety is the central authority of labour inspection, but from the legal and practical points of view, all labour inspection activities are decentralised in the provinces. The Department of Labour Inspection, Prevention and Safety acts as a regional department in charge of labour inspection activities within the capital and the other regional departments independent of it.

The inspection activities in the country do not follow any clear policy or strategy and there is an absence of collaboration among the different concerned institutions. The regional inspection activities are not under the supervision or control of a central authority of labour inspection. Inspection visits are

carried out according to an annual labour inspection programme, and monthly work report with results on labour inspection activities have to be prepared. However, the labour inspection activities are not planned at the national level.

There is no co-ordination between the National Social Security Fund and the Ministry of Labour.

The objectives of the Ministry of Labour are to reform the labour law to comply with the international standards and conventions, including the provisions related to labour inspection and to expand the labour and occupational safety and health inspection and services to ensure the compliance of the enterprises in the private sector with the labour legislations.

Recruitment and Selection

Methods and practices

The recruitment and selection process are subject to regulations, requirements for work permits in the case of non-Lebanese nationals. There are only relatively limited, general rules related to discrimination (see Discrimination) and Data Protection (see Data Protection). Recruitment and selection methods and practices are not specifically regulated or prohibited. All employees must provide evidence about their criminal records and pass a medical examination.

Discrimination

The Labour Law prohibits any discrimination that prejudices equal opportunity employment and equal access to jobs, though without specifying any particular grounds (sex, race, age, etc) on which such discrimination is unlawful (see Prohibition of Discrimination). The only specific rules on discrimination in recruitment apply to people with “special needs”. A Ministerial Decree stipulates that employers must not discriminate against such individuals in recruitment and selection. Job advertisements must not indicate any intention to discriminate against applicants with special needs. Employers must consider using a variety of channels to advertise vacancies and to receive job applications in order to include people with special needs. They must also consider adapting their selection procedures to give applicants with special needs the opportunity to demonstrate their capacities (i.e. giving them more time in interviews).

Probationary periods

There are two types of employees under the Lebanese labour law:

- the first includes all professional workers who hold office jobs; this includes everyone from administrative employees to senior managers
- the second category is comprised of manual labourers.

When employees are first hired, they are placed on a three-month probation period. After the trial period, the employer must pay at least the minimum wage which is 675.000 LBP per month.

During a probationary period, the employer and/or the employee may terminate the employment contract without having to give notice (see Notice Periods). The same employee may not serve more than one probationary period with the same employer nor can be renewed.

If the employee successfully completes the probationary period, it must be considered as part of the employee's period of continuous service with the employer.

During the probationary period, the employee is not entitled to benefit from any type of leave — even sick leave. If they want to take any leave, it will be considered as unpaid leave.

In case the employee takes service as a trainee, the employee as well as the employer shall be entitled to terminate the work contract without any prior notice or indemnity in the course of the three months following signing on.

Work permits and residency

A permit from the Ministry of Labour is required for foreigners to work in Lebanon. The Lebanese law entitles foreign workers, who are in possession of a work permit from the Ministry of Labour, to enjoy full social rights.

Free visas and temporary residence valid for a period of six months are granted on border departments and centres according to the following.

1. For Arab investors, businessmen and their family members who are visiting Lebanon for the first time for the purpose of investment, and that after presenting an official document from the appropriate authorities proving their professional occupation in addition to a recommendation letter from the same authorities in favour of granting the visa.
2. For Arab investors, businessmen and their family members holding a letter from the Investment Development Authority of Lebanon (IDAL) in favour of granting the visa.
3. For Arab investors, businessmen, traders and their family members pursuant to an invitation from a Lebanese businessman according to the following.

The inviting party presents an application to the General Directorate of General Security that should include:

- a written commitment to bring over the concerned party on the applicant's responsibility
 - a photocopy of his commercial record
 - a passport's photocopy of the invited person with an official document issued by the competent authorities certifying his professional occupation.
4. Investors and businessmen mentioned in articles 1–3 above, possessing a temporary residence for a period of six months and who have already launched investment projects in Lebanon, can present a request to the General Directorate of General Security to obtain a yearly or a permanent residence, valid for three years and renewable.
 5. For the citizens of the countries who have not granted immediate visas at the airport, their cases will be treated according to:
 - bankers, directors/general managers and employers after presenting a document that certifies their positions
 - people from Lebanese origin provided they present a proof
 - touristic delegations of minimum eight persons pursuant to an application presented by an authorised tourist company in Lebanon along with a departure commitment by that company.

Employment Contract

General principles

An employee may be employed only on the basis of an employment contract signed by both the employer and the employee. The employer must give the employee a copy of the signed written contract.

An employment contract is defined by the Labour Law as an agreement with a fixed or indefinite term concluded between an employer and an employee, whereby the latter commits to working for, and under the management and supervision of, the former in return for a wage that the employer is

committed to paying. An employee is defined as a person who works for, and under the management and supervision of, an employer in return for a wage of any kind (the definition includes employees).

The following are the Labour Law's main provisions on employment contracts.

- Employment contracts (and other employment-related documentation and instructions) must be in Arabic. If another language is also used, the Arabic text prevails in the event of any dispute.
- Employment contracts must in principle be in writing and in duplicate, with copies retained by the employee and the employer; if there is no written contract, any legal means of evidence may be used to prove that a contract exists and what its terms and conditions are.

Any employment contract that is not in writing is deemed to have an indefinite term.

All employment contracts must state:

- the names of the employer and employee
- the starting date of employment
- if the employment is not intended to be indefinite, its expected duration or, if it is a fixed term, the date when it is to end
- the job title or a brief description of the work
- the place of work
- the wages
- any terms and conditions relating to hours or days of work
- the notice period for termination.

Types of contract

An “employer” is defined as any person, natural or juridical, who is an industrial, trading, or agricultural enterprise employs an employee in some capacity to perform services for remuneration of any kind.

An “employee” is any man or woman who works in the service of another party for consideration of a wage or salary in an employer's premises, in accordance with an individual or group contract, written or oral.

It is forbidden to set adolescents, who have not yet completed their eighteenth year of age, to work more than six hours a day, with a break of at least one hour if the daily working period exceeds four consecutive hours.

An employment contract is defined as a contract of service or apprenticeship, whether oral or in writing, plus any permitted amendment or replacement thereof as agreed between the employer and employee. The written contract is to be written in Arabic; it may be, however, translated into a foreign language if the foreign employer does not know Arabic.

Employment contracts may have an indefinite or fixed term.

Based on the Labour Law, the maximum duration of a fixed-term contract is one year, automatically renewed.

Though this is not specifically regulated by the Labour Law, employment contracts can be for full-time or part-time work. No special rules generally apply to part-time contracts. The employee must sign special standard-format part-time employment contracts, using an official template, with the original and additional employers. The original employer is responsible for the employee's statutory benefits — notably annual leave (see Annual Leave).

General

Employers have general duties to:

- ensure, as far as is reasonably practicable, their employees' health, safety and welfare at work
- provide and maintain a workplace that is free of harassment, safe and without risks to employees' health.

Employees have duties to:

- perform their employment duties with reasonable diligence and care
- obey the employer's orders to the extent that these are consistent with the employee's employment duties and will not expose them to danger, and that carrying them out will not contravene any applicable regulation or legislation
- comply with the employer's health and safety instructions
- take reasonable care of any of the employer's property that is in the employee's possession or control or is accessed or used by the employee
- not compete with the employer's business
- not disclose to any third party any of the employer's confidential information, unless such disclosure is compelled by a competent court or applicable law (this obligation continues to apply indefinitely after employment ends).

Pay and Benefits

General pay principles

The payment of wages is an essential element of the employment contract. Wages are set by the employment contract. The Labour Law regulates matters such as payment of and deductions from wages. It defines the “wage” as whatever is given an employee in return for their service by virtue of an employment contract, whether in cash or in kind, a yearly, monthly, weekly, daily, hourly or piece basis. “Basic Salary” is defined as the wage stipulated in the employment contract, exclusive of any allowances.

An “allowance” is any allowance payable to an employee pursuant to an employment contract, including any housing, travel, education, social and entertainment allowances. An “additional payment” is any bonus, commission or other payment made by the employer that is discretionary, non-recurring or expressly agreed not to form part of the employee's wage or allowance. The employee's remuneration is the sum of the wage and any additional payments.

Payment of wages

The Labour Law stipulates:

- employees whose pay is calculated on an annual or a monthly wage must be paid at least once per month
- if any employee is paid on a monthly basis, the employer must not, without the employee's written agreement, change the basis of payment to weekly, daily, or hourly
- the wage or salary shall be paid in full during the delivery holiday of a pregnant employee
- an employee who has availed themselves of the ten-week delivery holiday, with full pay, has the right to receive the wage or salary for the period of the ordinary annual holiday, which may be obtained during the same year, in compliance with article 39 of the Code of Labour.

Transportation

Every employee receives 8000 LBP for every working day summing up to be 208,000 LBP per month. When the employee is on leave, s(he) will not benefit from the transportation.

Deductions

The Labour Law permits only the following deductions from wages:

- the social security contributions and income tax contributions (see NSSF Health Benefits)
- disciplinary fines imposed on the employee (see Disciplinary Matters)
- the repayment of debts to a third party, based on a court ruling; normally, the sums deducted for this reason must not exceed a quarter of the employee's wages but if there are numerous debts or debtors, up to half the wages may be deducted
- sums to pay for the repair or replacement of tools, machines, products or materials that have been lost, damaged or destroyed because the employee was at fault or breached the employer's instructions; the sums deducted for this reason must not exceed five days' wages per month.

National Social Security Fund

The National Social Security Fund (NSSF) provides employees with insurance coverage for sickness and maternity care. It also covers family allowances, end-of-service pension and work-related accidents and diseases. Any employee or labourer in any sector is eligible to enrol in the program. Employers are required to register all employees working for local and international firms with the NSSF. Foreign employees with a valid work permit and residence permits are entitled to join the NSSF, provided their home country offers equivalent or better programs to Lebanese residents employed there. Foreign Nationals are not entitled to end-of-service benefits.

Contributions

Employers must cover their employees' medical, family allowance and end-of-service indemnities contributions as follows:

- 6% of the salary toward family allowances (with a ceiling of 1,500,000 LL from the salary)
- 7% of the salary for health indemnity fund (with a ceiling of 1,500,000 LL from the salary)
- 8.5% of the salary for end-of-service fund (without any ceiling).

The employee contributes by 2% for health coverage with a monthly ceiling of LBP 30,000.

End of service

At the age of 60, an employee can ask for early retirement and end-of service compensation (paid only once) provided 20 years of service has been completed. Noting that the retirement age is 64, employees no longer benefit from the NSSF. An employee can continue working after 64 if the company's by-law allows it, but employees will no longer benefit from the end of service. The end-of-service indemnity will allow the employee to receive a month's wage equivalent to the last salary for every year worked.

Family and education allowances

Employees are entitled to family and education allowances, attached to the husband's rather than wife's salary, except if the female employee is a widow or sole provider.

A married employee registered with NSSF receives a spouse allowance of LBP 60,000 and an additional LBP 33,000 for every child (maximum 5 children); this amount is paid by the NSSF through the employers.

The transport allowance for every day they attend work is free of tax, and is not subject to NSSF contribution.

Schooling allowance

Schooling allowance, with a ceiling of LBP 1,500,000, is calculated on the basis of a lump sum, attending school or university.

This allowance does not form part of the NSSF employer contributions but is accounted for as operational expenses, and it is free of tax.

Employees of whatever category have children attending schools on a regular basis, be they private or public, or universities, will be granted yearly scholarships for each and every one of their children (males and females), and up to five children only, according to the following terms:

- amount of allowance:
 - LBP 300,000 for students in public schools
 - LBP 750,000 for students in private schools or universities
 - LBP 450,000 for students enrolled in the Lebanese university
- the allowance will be granted for every child who is three years of age directly before the beginning of the academic year, and does not exceed 25 years of age
- a female employee will not be granted such allowances, unless she has legal custody over the children and is cashing family allowances for them, or if the husband does not have the right, by virtue of the law, to obtain schooling allowances for their children; in addition, the female employee cashes the allowances difference in case the husband cashes a scholarship less than the amount stipulated in the Collective Labour Agreement.

NSSF health benefits

Once an employee is registered, the NSSF covers the employee and dependents in maternity, sickness, and work-related accidents.

The employee is liable for:

- 10% of all hospitalisation costs
- 20% of medication and examination expenses.

Exceptions are made for pre-maternity and post-maternity examinations, which the NSSF pays in full.

Compliance

The law requires all companies to contribute to the NSSF Fund. Companies with less than 10 employees have to submit reports and pay contributions every three months. Larger enterprises that contain more than 10 employees must submit their reports and settle their contributions on a monthly basis.

Evading the payments will impose penalties on the employer. Late payment penalties are calculated on a basis of 1 per thousand for each day of late payment of the contribution amount.

Minimum wages

The minimum wage is 675,000 LBP. The basic salary should be fully enrolled in the National Social Security Fund (NSSF) and Ministry of Finance.

Working Time, Rest and Holidays

Working hours and days

An employer may demand a maximum of 48 regular hours per week from an employee regardless of age or gender. This applies to all business except agriculture. Under special circumstances, employers

can add extra hours to an employee's regular shift, but this requires a permit from the Ministry of Labour and that:

- the Social Affairs service is informed within 24 hours of the intervening case and of the time necessary to perform the work
- the wage or salary for the overtime provided by the wage-earner or salary-earner is 50% higher than the rate of normal hours.

Any hours that exceed the statutory limits for normal working time are considered to be overtime.

A normal working day should be eight hours, and in some cases up to 12 hours, knowing that employees should be given nine consecutive hours of rest between each working day.

All employees are to be granted a weekly rest which must not be under 36 unbroken hours.

Rest breaks and rest periods

The employer is to select the day of this rest generally on Sundays or distribute it among the employees in sympathy with the requirements of the work especially in the operations departments.

Breaks do not count as working hours. Special rules on breaks apply to factories and workshops where work is carried out in successive shifts around the clock, and operations that require uninterrupted work for technical and economic reasons.

Whenever the duration of work exceeds six non-stop hours for men and five non-stop hours for women, the employer is required to allow these employees in the middle of the day, a rest-time which is not to be under one hour.

Annual leave

Employees are entitled (under the Labour Law) to paid annual leave after they have completed one year's service with an employer.

During the first year of service, they have no entitlement until they complete one year's service. Leave must generally be taken in the year when the employee accrues the entitlement.

The employer may determine when the employee takes annual leave.

During annual leave, the employer must pay the employee their basic wage and any housing allowance that forms part of their remuneration.

The employer is forbidden from dismissing an employee or giving them notice of dismissal during annual leave.

Employees who have completed one year of employment are entitled to an annual leave according to their period of employment with full pay:

- 15 days from 1 (completed year) till 5 years of employment
- 17 days from 5 till 10 years of employment
- 19 days from 10 till 15 years of employment
- 21 days for more than 15 years of employment.

The employer may choose the date of these leaves in sympathy with the requirements of service. The employer may not dismiss the wage-earner or salary-earner nor serve him with dismissal notice while his leave is in progress.

Bereavement leave

- Employees are granted a paid leave up to two days in the event of the death of a first level relative (father, mother, spouse, child, grandchild, sister, brother, grandfather or grandmother) with full pay.
- Employees are granted a paid leave up to 1 day in the event of the death of a 2nd level relative (uncle, aunt, cousin, niece, nephew, brother-in-law, sister-in-law, father-in-law, or mother-in-law).
- Proof document (obituary paper) should be provided to the HR department when the employee resumes work.

Marriage leave

Employees are granted a one-week paid leave for their marriage, and this is *only* for “one time” during their employment with the company.

Public holidays

Employees are entitled to a paid day off on official public holidays.

An employer may require an employee to work on a public holiday, if circumstances make this necessary. In such cases, the employer must grant the employee a day off on another day and pay their normal rate.

Fitr Feast	Varies according to Calendar
Adha Feast	Varies according to Calendar
Islamic New Year	Varies according to Calendar
Independence Day	22 November
New Year Day	1 January
Ashoura	Varies according to Calendar
Christmas	25 December
Prophet's Birthday	Varies according to Calendar
Easter Sunday	Varies according to Gregorian and West Calendar
Orthodox Easter	Varies according to Gregorian and West Calendar
Labour Day	1 May
Resistance and Liberation Day	25 May
Assumption Day	15 August

Parenthood and Work-life Balance**Maternity leave**

- Pregnant employees are entitled to a paid maternity leave of absence for 10 consecutive weeks; this period will include the days before and after delivery date.
- The employee who has availed themselves of the ten-week delivery holiday, with full pay, has the right to receive the wage or salary for the period of ordinary annual holiday, which may be obtained during the same year, in compliance with article 39 of the Code of Labour.

An employer must not dismiss (or give notice of dismissal to) an employee who is pregnant or on maternity leave or send any warning. Any such dismissal will be deemed to be “arbitrary” and the employee may claim compensation (see Arbitrary Dismissal).

Paternity leave

Employees are entitled to a paid leave up to three days when they give birth. Every company reserves the right to grant this leave.

Sick leave

If the employee is afflicted with a disease other than the diseases of their trade or labour accidents covered by Decree-Law No. 25/ ET of 4 May 1943, they shall be entitled to sick leave if they have completed three months' service with their employer after the completion of any probationary period as follows:

- half a month with full pay and half a month with half pay for the wage-earner or salary-earner who had three months' service or more up to two years' service
- one month with full pay and one month with half pay for the wage-earner or salary-earner who has had more than two years' service and up to four years' service
- one month and a half with full pay and one month and a half with half pay for the employees who have had more than four years' service up to six years' service
- two months with full pay and two months with half pay for the employees who have had more than six years' service up to ten years' service
- two months and a half with full pay and two months and a half with half pay for the employees who have had more than ten years' service.

The employee must notify the employer of the sickness absence as soon as reasonably practicable on the first day of absence and at least once every three days during the absence.

Sick leaves shall be granted on the evidence of a medical report covering the entire period of absence either of the employees' attending doctor, or the doctor of the organisation. The employer is entitled to have the certificate produced by the employees checked by a medical examiner.

These sick leaves may be renewed in the course of the year as many times as is necessary until the maximum time limits listed above. If these leaves exceed one month, the employer is entitled to reduce the annual leave up to eight days.

The employer may not dismiss the employee nor serve on him a dismissal notice while he is on sick leave.

If an employee on sick leave works for another employer during the leave, the main employer is entitled to dismiss the employee and withhold payment for the leave.

Equality and Discrimination

Prohibition of discrimination

The Labour Law prohibits any discrimination that prejudices equal opportunity employment, equal access to jobs, equal continuity of employment or equal enjoyment of rights, and bans discrimination between employees with the same work duties. This general prohibition does not specify any particular grounds on which discrimination is unlawful (i.e. sex, race or age).

The employer may not discriminate between working men and women with regard to:

- type of work
- amount of wage or salary
- employment
- promotion
- professional qualifications
- apparel.

Employees' obligations and rights

Employers have general duties to:

- ensure, as far as is reasonably practicable, their employees' health, safety and welfare at work
- provide and maintain a workplace that is without risks to employees' health and safety.

They must, as far as is reasonably practicable:

- ensure adequate systems are in place that minimise risks to health relating to fire hazards and the use, handling, storage and transport of dangerous articles and substances
- provide information, instruction, training and supervision to employees, in English or, if necessary, another language understood by the employees, to ensure their health and safety at work
- inform each employee in writing at the time of recruitment of the dangers, if any, connected with the employment and of the protective measures the employee must take
- provide and maintain adequate and safe access to, and from, the workplace
- provide any other facilities or meet any other requirements as prescribed in OHS rules/regulations.

Termination of Employment

Termination by the employer

The employer may terminate by giving a required notice and giving a severance pay and may also dismiss an employee without notice on certain misconduct-related grounds.

However, if the employer dismisses an employee with notice for “arbitrary” reasons, the employee may claim compensation.

The employer and the employee shall each have a right to terminate at any time the work contract of unspecified duration concluded between them.

However, in case of misuse or abuse of this right, the aggrieved party shall be entitled to claim indemnity assessed in conformity with the following bases.

- In case termination comes from the employer, indemnity shall be assessed in accordance with the:
 - nature of the job
 - employee's age
 - employee's service period
 - employee's family status
 - employee's health condition
 - scope of the prejudice and the extent of misuse of that right

On condition that indemnity as awarded by the Court shall be neither less than the wages of two months nor higher than the wages of 12 months over and above those indemnities reverting to the employee due to the fact of the dismissal.

- In case termination comes from the employee on grounds other than those authorised by the law, and if it should be proved that has caused prejudice or embarrassment to the employer, indemnity for damages shall be valued at the equivalent of between one and four months' wages depending on the case, over and above the indemnity.

The party who should deem that the termination is the outcome of misuse or abuse of right, shall have to institute proceedings to this result before the Conciliation Board within a time limit of one month dating from the notification of termination with all modes of evidence.

The Conciliation Board shall adjudicate within a maximum time limit of three months.

The party who should breach the provisions of the preceding paragraph shall be liable to pay to the other party an indemnity equal to the amount of wages of the time limit of notice set by law.

Summary dismissal

An employer is entitled to dismiss an employee without notice if the employee:

- claims a false identity or nationality, or submits false certificates or documents
- is undergoing a probationary period (see Probationary Periods)
- commits an error that results in major material losses to the employer; however, the employer is required to inform in writing the Social Affairs Service of this violation within three days of the organisation of the fact
- has been convicted of an act or rendered himself guilty of a deliberate negligence with intent to cause material damage to the employer's prejudice
- fails to perform their main duties in accordance with the employment contract and does not remedy such a failure despite written warnings of the matter; repeated warnings which have been served to the employee in writing three times in the course of a single offence will lead to lawful termination
- reveals any business secrets related to the company where the employee is employed
- is found during working hours to be in a state of drunkenness or under the influence of narcotics
- has been sentenced to a year's imprisonment or more for a crime they have committed or if they have been guilty of an offence on the premises of their work and during work hours
- has been condemned for facts or acts designated and sanctioned by article 344 of the Penal Code
- assaults the employer, a manager or another employee in the course of work
- is absent without valid cause for more than seven consecutive days, or more than 15 non-consecutive days in one year; the employer must give the employee written warning of the number of days during which the employee was absent, otherwise, the case will be considered groundless
- commits an unprovoked assault on the employer on the premises.

On the other hand, the employee is entitled to leave work before the date provided for in the contract and without prior notice if the employer:

- has deceived the employee as to the conditions of work at the time when the contract was concluded; but the employee loses his right from such argument if thirty days have passed since his starting date
- does not honour his obligations towards the employee in conformity with the requirements of the Labour Law
- commits a misdemeanour offence on the person of the employee or on a member of his family
- is guilty of assault on the employee's person.

External factors

The employer shall be entitled to terminate all or part of his organisation's work contracts in the event of force majeure or of compelling economic or technical circumstances, such as reduction of the size of the organisation.

The employer shall be required to notify the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs of any intent to terminate those contracts one month prior to the execution and shall equally be required to consult the Ministry of Labour on the scheduling of laying off the employees, taking into consideration employees' seniority in the organisation, their specialisation, their age, their family and social status, and finally the means deemed necessary for their re-hiring.

Employees laid off due to an external factor as stated above, shall have the benefit, within one year of their discharge, of priority for being re-hired in the organisation from which they were laid off if work is resumed normally.

Equally benefiting from the dismissal indemnity, the woman employee who is bound to leave service due to marriage on condition that she serves advance notice, is served to the employer within the notice period and that the employee has been employed for more than one year. The indemnity is payable only when marriage has been established.

Retirement

The employee of 60 years of age or who has 25 years' service in the same organisation may, on request, be dismissed and benefit from the dismissal indemnity.

This same employee also has the right to continue to work until the age of 64 years; at this age, the employee's subjection to the provisions of the Code of Labour, and therefore to the rules regarding dismissal indemnity, shall end, unless the organisation where the employee works or the group work contract allows work beyond the age of 64 years.

If an employee requests the payment of indemnity at the age of 60 or after 25 years' service in the same organisation, they shall have no right to a new dismissal indemnity in case they stay in employment until the age of 64.

Final settlement

The pay to be taken for the assessment of indemnities referred to is the last one paid before dismissal for the dismissal advance notice.

Pay is understood to be the basic remuneration calculated at the time and encashed by the employee as well as the allowances and commissions added to the basic pay.

If pay was calculated in whole or in part on the basis of commission, account shall be taken of the average sum actually encashed by the employee during the twelve-month period before dismissal.

Arbitrary dismissal

If an employer dismisses with notice an employee on an indefinite-term contract, this is considered "arbitrary" if the cause of termination is not "related to the work". It is specifically arbitrary to dismiss an employee for filing a serious complaint against the employer with the public authorities, or bringing a valid claim against the employer, or to dismiss a pregnant employee.

"Arbitrary" is not otherwise defined by the Labour Law or other statutes. In practice, dismissals generally tend to be found not to be arbitrary if related to misconduct, poor performance, redundancy or business reasons, and if the employer has followed appropriate and fair procedures, i.e. the constitutional disciplinary procedure (see Disciplinary Matters) in the case of a disciplinary dismissal.

One or several Arbitration Boards shall be set up in each Governorate to have jurisdiction on disputes taking place between the employer and employee regarding matters, specifically terminations.

This Board shall be composed of:

- a judge, of the 11th grade or above:
 - to be appointed by Decree on the proposal of the Minister of Justice
 - after the approval of the Higher Council of the Bench
- an employer's representative and a worker's representative:
- to be appointed by Decree on the proposal of the Minister of Labour and Social Affairs.

Another two deputy members will be appointed, one representing the employer and the other representing the employees, in case of absence or excuse, by decree on the proposal of the Minister of Labour and Social Affairs.

The acting representatives of employers and employees must meet the following conditions:

- have a Lebanese nationality
- are 20 years of age
- have suffered no conviction for dishonourable offences or crimes
- have carried on their profession for at least five years.

The arbitration Board deals with:

- disputes arising from the assessment of the minimum pay
- disputes arising from labour accidents covered by Legislative Decree No. 25 of 4 May 1943
- disputes arising from dismissal, negligence of work, and fines.

Such disputes are exempted from juridical fees; as with Court expenses, these are borne by the losing party.

Resignation

An employee may terminate an indefinite-term employment contract at any time by giving the employer the required notice, or payment in lieu (see Notice Periods). An employee is entitled to resign without notice if the employer breaches its legal or contractual obligations towards the employee, or if the employer or its legal representative assaults the employee; in such cases, the employee can seek compensation, as for arbitrary dismissal (see Arbitrary Dismissal).

Notice periods

Notice periods must be given in writing.

During a notice period, the employee must be paid their full wages and must continue to carry out their job, unless the employer does not require this.

The employer or employee may pay the other party in lieu of all or part of the notice period, at the employee's normal wage rate.

The employer and the employee shall each be required to advise the other of intent to terminate the contract as follows:

- one month in advance in the case of the employment duration being more than three months and less than three years
- two months in advance in the case of the employment duration being more than three years and less than six years
- three months in advance in the case of the employment duration being more than six years and less than twelve years
- four months in advance in the case of the employment duration being more than twelve years.

The dismissal notice period may not be served on:

- the expecting mother
- the woman on delivery holiday
- any employee on ordinary holiday or on sick leave.

However, the employer is not obliged by these restrictions if the employee has found employment elsewhere in the course of the said holiday.

If the employer fails to comply with the rules regarding the dismissal notice, he shall have to pay the employee the wage or salary for the days comprised in the time limit of the notice, or those for the days during which the dismissal notice may not be served.

Prior notice shall be affected in writing and shall be notified to the interested party; the latter shall be entitled to require clarification of the causes on which termination is grounded if such causes are not indicated in the text of the notice.

Other forms of termination

The employer and employee can terminate the employment contract at any time by mutual consent, as long as the employee's consent is expressed in writing.

The employment contract terminates on the employee's death or medically certified total disability. If the employer is an individual, the employment contract does not automatically terminate on their death, unless the contract relates to the employer's person.

End-of-service

Employees who have at least one year's service (excluding any days of unpaid absence) are in many circumstances entitled under the Labour Law to a statutory "End-of-Service Gratuity/ Indemnity" on termination of employment.

- The gratuity is neither calculated as less than wages of two months nor higher than the wages of twelve months over and above those indemnities reverting to the employee due to the fact of the dismissal.
- The wages on which the gratuity is calculated exclude all bonuses and allowances, overtime pay and payments in kind.
- The gratuity included the notice period (see Notice Periods).
- The gratuity included the annual leaves entitled to the dismissed employee.

Where the employer dismisses an eligible employee, they are entitled to a statutory end-of-service gratuity except in the case of summary dismissal on valid grounds (see Summary Dismissal).

In case termination comes from the employee on grounds other than those authorised by the law, and if it should be proved that has caused prejudice or embarrassment to the employer, indemnity for damages shall be valued at the equivalent of between one and four months' wages depending on the case, over and above the indemnity.

Challenging dismissals

If an employee believes that they have been arbitrarily dismissed (see Arbitrary Dismissal), summarily dismissed without justification (see Summary Dismissal), or dismissed without the due notice or procedure, they may make a complaint to the Ministry of Labour, which will seek to broker an amicable settlement. If this is unsuccessful, the Ministry may authorise the employee to bring a case in the labour courts.

If the court finds that an employee has been arbitrarily dismissed or without justification, it may order the employer to pay compensation to the employee. The court bases the compensation on the type of work, the extent of damages incurred to the employee, the duration of employment and the work conditions.

Disciplinary matters

The Labour Law permits the employer to impose the following disciplinary sanctions.

- Verbal Warning and Written Warnings
 - Written warnings which have been served to the employee three times during a single offence will lead to lawful termination.
 - Every warning should be submitted to the Ministry of Labour within a three-day time frame after the employer and the employee sign on it. The employee reserves the right to sign or not to sign. In the case of no signature, the employer can write “the employee has been served and abstained to sign”
 - The warnings must be submitted, signed and stamped at the Ministry of Labour.
 - A copy will be given to the employer to be saved in the employee's personal file.
- Fines due to negligence of work or any misconduct or misuse, which may be set as a specific amount; the fine for a single disciplinary offence must not exceed three days' pay and the sums deducted from pay in respect of fines must not exceed five days' wages per month.

Fines are no longer applicable if fifteen days have passed on the violation or misconduct of the employee. The fines' details shall be saved in the employee's file and the payroll:

- the name of the employee
- the nature of his offence
- the date
- the importance of the penalty.

An employer may make deductions from an employee's wages to pay for the repair or replacement of tools, machines, products or materials that have been lost, damaged or destroyed because the employee was at fault or breached the employer's instructions. If it does so, it must not impose a disciplinary sanction for the same fault or breach.

However, in no case can the sums withheld exceed in a single month the amount of five days' pay.

- Dismissal with a full end-of-service gratuity
- Dismissal with no end-of-service gratuity; this is permitted only in the circumstances where summary dismissal is valid (see Summary Dismissal).

An employer must not impose a disciplinary sanction on an employee unless it has notified them in writing of the charges, heard and investigated the employee's defense, and recorded the matter (and the sanction imposed) in their personal file.

An employer must not impose more than one disciplinary sanction for the same offence.

Data protection

Data privacy is protected in a general manner by the Penal Code, which makes it a criminal offence to use or disclose individuals' personal data without their consent. Under the Civil Code, an individual whose rights are breached in this way may bring a court case seeking compensation/damages and/or an order to end the infringement. There is no specific legislation on data protection in the employment context but the Penal Code's provisions indicate that employers can collect and use personal data only with the consent of the employee or job applicant concerned.

Record keeping, rules and regulations

Employers that employ at least five employees must (under the Labour Law) keep a file for each employee, stating their name, occupation, age, nationality, address, marital status, date of employment, wages (and any adjustments to them), any disciplinary sanctions penalties imposed, and occupational injuries and diseases sustained, and the date of and reasons for termination of employment. The file must include a leave card, recording annual leave, sick leave and other leave taken.

Employers that employ at least 15 employees must keep at every workplace:

- a payroll record stating for all employees the date employment started and ended, the days worked, the amount of daily, weekly or monthly wages paid, fringe benefits and any piecework or commission payments
- a record of all occupational injuries and diseases sustained
- “basic work regulations”, approved by the public labour authorities and displayed prominently, stating the daily working hours, the weekly rest period, public holidays, and the measures and precautions taken for the prevention of occupational injuries and fire hazards
- disciplinary rules, approved by the public labour authorities and displayed prominently, stating the applicable disciplinary offences and sanctions (see Disciplinary Matters).

ONE FINAL WORD!

Lebanon: From Switzerland of the Middle East to modern-day dystopia!

After years of delusory economic policies enforced by a corrupt elite, Lebanon is experiencing a painful awakening. The coffers of a nation long renowned as the Switzerland of the Middle East are empty, the underbelly of its banking system - delivering artificial interest rates - exposed, and the Lebanese people given a full reality check, two years into the Lebanese economic catastrophe.

The economy's rapid deterioration has shattered Lebanese society, plunging sections of the working class, middle class, poor, and well-off into poverty and toppling a financial system described as a nationally supervised Ponzi scheme.

Following the civil war in Lebanon from 1975 to 1990, successive governments implemented financial engineering policies in an attempt to reclaim Lebanon's former reputation as the Middle East's Switzerland, a distinction owed more to the banking secrecy of its financial institutions than to its mountains.

This utopian linkage has given rise to a very real dystopia today: the myth of the Lebanese economic miracle, culminating in the monetary curse of the central bank governor, Riad Salameh, a man formerly referred to as a "financial genius." The illusion has worn off, and with the onset of the country's worst-ever socioeconomic crisis - including the civil war years - it is evident that Lebanon's central bank governor has stepped over to the dark side.

The once Middle Eastern stronghold is now nothing more than a piggy bank with a padlock for those who didn't get their cash under their mattress in time. The country has become a vast theatre, where depositors and bankers are engaged in a strange and cruel conflict.

Why Lebanon's internal collapse seems unstoppable

Savers are being shut out of dollar accounts or told that the monies they may access are worth less in this bizarre circumstance. "This is not a dollar," the Lebanese may well reason, for not only are withdrawals limited, but greenbacks in the country of cedars are instantaneously changed into multi-colored piles of worthless Lebanese pounds. In other words, a clutch of Monopoly money in a game where only the depositors go to jail - sentenced for daring to try to undermine the system one October evening in 2019.

Growing unlawful financial practices and bank closures in the aftermath of the popular uprising in October 2019 may have accelerated the Lebanese crisis, but danger had been festering for some time. International investments had already dried up, and the cash looted for years by a corrupt elite lubricating the Lebanese financial system had already sailed to more pleasant shores - offshore tax havens, as some would call them.

While the country devolves into inexorable bankruptcy, the usual suspects sit pretty and unconcerned, mutually absolving themselves of any wrongdoing and clinging to the reins of power of a non-existent state - even if it means sacrificing Lebanon's entire population in the name of political survival. When you strike a bargain with the devil, though, you have to live with the consequences!

Legends and dystopias are the stuff of fiction, and trusting them too much might lead to delusional behavior. Truth is stranger than fiction, as the shocking degradation of Lebanon over the last two years has demonstrated. The tale of Lebanon could begin as follows: Once upon a time, there was a country renowned as the Middle East's Switzerland. And, to be honest, that's where the story ends.

Lebanon as we previously knew it, the Middle East's Switzerland, with Beirut as the Middle East's Paris, is no longer! I never imagined I'd live to see the end of Lebanon, but that's exactly what we're seeing right now! Since 2019, the currency has lost over 90% of its value; 78 percent of the population is estimated to be poor; severe fuel and diesel shortages exist; society is on the verge of collapsing; the population is physically, psychologically, and emotionally exhausted, and life has been reduced to the necessities of survival.

Sitting down to work is nearly impossible because my laptop's battery only lasts for so long. In my community, government-supplied energy is only accessible for 2 to 3 hours per day, and private community generators only run for maximum 10 hours before shutting down at midnight until morning. As a result, I'm behind on every deadline, and I've sent a lot of sorry emails. I'm not sure what I'm supposed to say at this point. "My nation is falling"!

Nowadays, Lebanese people who do not want to risk attempting the perilous Mediterranean crossing are swarming in government offices to get visas for any potential destination. They're looking beyond the water, where the blaze of green, the green light of promise - and the dollar - beckons.

Because the almighty greenback is the ticket out of Lebanon, Lebanese people carefully stash their dollars (at home) while waiting for the big departure. The dollar, Lebanon's lifeline, is traded on the underground market at a rate that is changing the country's society. Simply ask, "What currency are you paid in?" to distinguish the former rich from the new poor!

In the end, many Lebanese have chosen to say their final goodbyes, creeping to the airport like tortoises, their houses on their backs, after admirably sticking in for so long.